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A STUDY ON IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION OVER THE BANKING SECTOR WITH REFERENCE TO VERAVAL CITY

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to investigate about the impact of the demonetization over the banking sector. The study covers the banking sectors of specially veraval city. For the study I had selected total 13 banks of veraval city. Further for the study aspect I had chosen the structured questioner, which was filled up by bank employees. To grab the knowledge I asked them questions related to the black money, online banking, accounts of banks which highly affected, Government's preparation for post demonetization situation as well as customer's preference to keep money either at home or bank. By analysing the data collected almost 55% employees agreed with the view of positive impact of demonetization. Highly affected accounts were saving a/c and current account. Almost 51% employees had opinion that customers are moving towards online banking. 52% employees said black money which is in form of cash has been curbed by government. 69% employees were positive about customer behaviour on keeping money at bank. By seeing all areas mentioned above I can say that as compare to previous two demonetization, this one is successful. Still as compare to short terms, more positive impacts can be seen in long term. Though this paper is only having data of veraval city banks it can be used for further analysis in this area.

KEY WORDS: Corruption, banks, black money, post demonetization effect, online banking, veraval

INTRODUCTION

Concept of Demonetization:

Demonetization is the act of removing the current currency from the economy and replacing it with the new one. It is the step taken up by the Government generally with the motive of removal of corruption. Moreover it is the act of depriving of value of currency for official payment. It does not only include the currency but also include the precious metals. Originally Demonetization is the French word "demonetiser" dating back to 1850-55.

The reasons for the Demonetization are. To fight with inflation, to beat the corruption, to remove counterfeit currency and to discourage the cash system. Developing country like India has to find the solution of problems like this for betterment of country.

In 1982, Ghana took the decision to demonetize their 50 cedi currency. Which created chaos and the decision was not well comed. Afterwards Nigeria (in 1984), Myanmar (in 1987) , Soviet Union(1991) , North korea and Zimbabwe had also took this type of decision in past.

HISTORY OF DEMONETIZATION IN INDIA:

It is not the first time in history, that government has taken this kind of step. It has been happen twice in the past. The first currency ban was announced as on 12th January, 1946(Saturday) by RBI headquarter. At that time currency notes of 1000 and 10,000 were totally removed from economy. Both the notes were re-introduced in year 1954. At that time people had given 10 days time period to exchange the notes. Further that was extended to 15 days more where by people has to give reasons why they had not exchanged it in previous 10

days. It had not created much effect at that time. By the end of 1947 out of Rs.143.97 crores, notes of only Rs. 134.9 crores were exchanged. Thus notes worth Rs. 9.07 were perhaps “Demonetised”.

The second currency ban was made on 16th January, 1978(Monday), announced by R. Janaki Raman a senior official of RBI, and at the time of Morarji Desai led Janata party. At that time currency ban was taken 1000, 5000 and 10,000 out of circulation. That time the people had given only 3 days to exchange the notes. This time around 73.1 crore was demonetised.

Finally the 3rd, the most recent demonetization had been announced as on 8th November, 2016 by Prime Minister Narendra Modi. This time the currency of 500 and 1000 notes are demonetized from economy. The Government has instructed the hospitals, petrol pumps, airports etc to accept the old denomination notes till 11th November, 2016.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Mr Brijesh Singh and Dr. N. Babitha Thimmaiah (January 2017) in their research paper studied the effect of demonetization in terms of “Won or lost”. By using the secondary data method i.e. articles, they had conducted their study. In the study report they had tried to explain the concept of cashless economy by taking the reference of Woodford (2003). It is not all about how much money you are having in your wallet, you can pay by any of the bank card or banking transfer. In the research paper they had show the effect of demonetization in the areas like, cash rush, stock market, transportation, agriculture, banking, business, income tax, railways etc. There are no exact proofs of exact black money holding in cash but studies show that around 8% of black money is held in cash. According to the Centre for Monitoring the Indian Economy (CMIE), the transaction cost of demonetization until 30th December, 2016 is estimated around Rs. 1.28 lakh crore. As per R. Gandhi, Deputy Governor of RBI, speaking on 7th December 2016, Rs. 11.5 lakh crore has been already deposited at bank out of total 14.5 lakh crore which means still 3 lakh crore are unidentified.

Geeta Rani (November 2016) had presented the research paper to show the effect of demonetization over the retail outlets. She had done her research work by taking the primary data. She had used the Questionnaire method. This was filled by the 50 shopkeepers of the area. As a result she had been ready with some out comes likewise 80% shopkeeper presented their view that from 9th November, 2016 to 10th December, 2016 there was 20% increase in sales due to accepting the old notes. But after that sales had declined. Shopkeeper started paytm and cheque system. Shopkeepers had extended credit period. Top brands like HUL, P&G had affected with only decrease of 20% sales due to brand name. Moreover on the basis of the study she had identified the effect of demonetization category wise. Likewise, salty snacks sale decreased by 10%, chocolates sales had decreased by 50%, biscuits sales had decreased by 20%, juice/fruit drinks sales decreased by 20%, cigarettes sales decreased by 10%, mobile phones sales decreased by 70% , gold sales increased by 70% and durable goods sales decreased by 70%. She concluded her paper by giving the views that though demonetization is painful for short term, but it will surely beneficial for the long run moreover most customers are now adopting cashless means like paytm, debit card, cheques etc.

Sherline T.I (December 2016) has undertaken the research on “Demonetization as a prelude to complete financial inclusion “. The main objective of the study was to understand the importance of demonetization as a measure of financial inclusion. Financial inclusion mainly stands for, the delivery of the financial services at the affordable cost to the low income segments of society. As per the report financial inclusion can boost the savings as well as credit availability. The study shows that this move of the Government has likely to create long term benefits. Moreover medium to long term Current account and Saving account (CASA) ratio could improve. Moreover demonetization would reduce cash transaction the real estates, which may decrease the price of that avenues which make it affordable to general public. Moreover the near future inflation will decrease due to less cash transaction.

M. Angel Jasmine Shirley (February, 2017) has studied about the “Impact of Demonetization in India” in her research paper. In the first part of the paper, the impact over Indian economy had been explained. As per the research, the BSE SENSEX and NIFTY 50 stock had been fall near about 6% on the very next day. Moreover on the later on days, the country felt severe shortage of the cash. Moreover due to lack of cash overall production had decreased. Banks had not enough new currency for the exchange of the old notes, which breakdown the overall economic system. Moreover in the paper impact of the demonetization over world economy also shown. The first thing that happened after demonetization was decrement in to overall consumption of commodities which results in to decrease in the export-import. Moreover there was a major impact over the domestic sectors, reduction in the Government liability, farming and fishing industry, business, drop in industrial output, black money, impact over counterfeit currency, hawala, bank deposits, jewellery and

real estate, IT sector etc. Findings in this sectors says that, though demonetization is a good concept to grab the black money holders, most of black money is kept in form of land, gold, real estate etc. “Not all black money is in cash, not all cash is black money”. People face too much inconveniency due to improper planning about post demonetization. Moreover for number of days they had spent their time by standing in queues. To decline over all negative impact of it, ways are to focusing over tax aspect, cash availability, and elimination of loopholes.

Chabi Gupta (December 2016) had studied about the payment banks and demonetization. To explain her research point, she had firstly explaiend about the Indian banking sector. Payment banks are generally niche banking set up by RBI , payment banks provides small saving accounts and payment services mainly for low income household, small businesses etc. Then she had explained the overall impact of demonetization move. According to the Reserve Bank Of India (RBI) figures, as of March 2016 currencies in circulation amounted to Rs.16,415 billion of this 500 notes were of around 47.8%in value and 1000 were of 38.6% in value. Jointly they had 86% value in the economy. Many banks like HDFC, ICICI and AXIS are exploring to launch the contact less debit and credit card. It will allow the customers to use card without swiipe.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research methodology is the activity of collecting the information and data, with the intention of doing the research. Methodology may include different tools like research objective, sampling, sampling methods etc. It is a broad area which covers the most aspects of research.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The key role of the researcher is to set the clear, unambiguous objectives of the study which may prove helpful for the understanding the study. By keeping in mind this fact I had set the following goals.

- i) To understand the effect of demonetization in terms of positive or negative.
- ii) To identify those accounts which are highly affected due to demonetization.
- iii) To check the awareness of online banking among consumers
- iv) To understand about people’s attitude for keeping the money either at home or at bank.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Research design states the overall strategy adopted by the researcher where by overall components of the study are set out in the logical way. That effectively presents the problem of the study moreover it constitute the collection, measurement and analysis of the data in the systematic way.

For the study of impact of demonetization I had used descriptive research method. Motive behind choosing this tool is that this method is useful in describing the data that analysed through study. Moreover descriptive study can provide you the overall knowledge about the specific sector in an analytical way.

SAMPLE DESIGN:

If researcher is going through the total population for the research then it may take the huge amount of time. So it is convenient to take the sample from the population. Sampling is the tool of selecting the sample from population. Research done over here is by using the Convenient Sampling Method. For the research purpose I had focused over Veraval city as the population. Of which 100 sample size has been selected. Respondents are the employees of the 13 selected bank of veraval.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data collection is the most important part of any of the research. Generally primary as well as secondary ways are available for data collection. For this study primary data collection has been used. For that Questioner method has been used by me. Where in I personally approached the respondents with the view to gather the information from them.

Interpretation:

51% employees had positive opinion about the impact on online banking. Moreover the employees who were agree or highly agree with increased use of online banking, had given reason that customers are using the mobile app also now to pay money. One of the BOB employees gave the name of the application i.e. “M connect plus”

3. Do you think Government has not prepared enough for the post demonetization situation?

- A) Highly agree B) Agree C) Neutral
 D) Disagree E) Highly disagree

Sr. No	Options	No. Of responses
1	Highly agree	18
2	Agree	17
3	Neutral	20
4	Disagree	20
5	Highly disagree	25
Total		100

Interpretation:

From the above graphical presentation I can say that there is a mixed opinion about the preparation of Government for the post demonetization. Some of the employees said government done whatever was required. Where as some had opposite opinion of it.

FINDINGS:

I had asked some more questions to the employees, which gave me some more findings mentioned below.

1. In a question where I asked them about highest impacted a/c of bank. 35% employees had opinion about the savings a/c, 30% had about cash deposit and withdrawal a/c and 20%, 8% and 7% respectively for Current a/c, cash credit a/c and other a/c which includes loan a/c.
2. More over in a question of opinion for ‘Demonetization- a tool for curbing the black money’. Almost 52% employees said Yes ,demonetization is a good tool for curbing black money. Some of them had explained that Black money is not only in form of cash. It may be in form of property, gold, land etc. If we are purely talking about black money in form of cash, then it may be a good tool.
3. Further I asked about people’s behaviour either to keep money at home or bank. Almost 69% employees said that gradually people are now moving towards banks. Further they said so many ladies are there. Who came first time to bank and seen the work of bank and learned cash deposit and all other regular tasks.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Despite of having a complete analysis of the topic, this research is having some of the limitation. Those are as follows.

- i) This study covers only few banks of the Veraval city, which may not provide the complete picture of the effect of demonetization over banking sector.
- ii) Moreover demonetization is the very latest topic to study, due to that not enough research papers are available in this sector to study.
- iii) Some respondents didn’t show the interest to fill the questioner.
- iv) Moreover this topic requires a very depth research whereas here only 100 respondents have taken so it may not enough for this study.

CONCLUSION:

By seeing the data collected over here, I can say that, this time demonetization has proven somehow more successful as compare to previous two. Wind has been change. People became more conscious about online banking. Bank employees had work continuously without taking day off. Their co-operation matters a lot. Though total black money had not been grabbed by this tool, this tool proves fruitful for at least creating fear in the minds of black money holders. It was compulsory for the Government to take some steps like demonetization to decrease corruption, terrorism, black money etc.

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